

TOLERANCE OF NEWLY CREATED RIDGES TO CERTAIN BIOTIC FACTORS, MORPHO-ECONOMY AND FIBER QUALITY INDICATORS

Anisa Barotova Razzakovna

Independent researcher Tashkent State Agrar University
Xurramov Asilbek Abdusamat o'g'li

Independent researcher Tashkent State Agrar University
Ismoilov Imomali Nozimjon o'g'li

Tashkent State Agrar University student

Yigitaliyeva Mushtariy Farhodjon qizi

Tashkent State Agrar University student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7824161>

Abstract.

Keywords: Gossypium hirsutum, method, cotton, varieties, plant, cultivat, fiber, maturity; micronaire, fiber, length, color grade, database, regional, climatic.

It is known that cotton grows on a total area of 30 million hectares every year is cultivated. The value of a selected cotton variety is its quality and fiber yield is determined by. Continuous development of agriculture and technology in the countryside demands for new varieties of agricultural crops are increasing. As a result, valuable breeding materials are created that are resistant to germs, water shortages, insects and pests and other factors. As a result of this, valuable breeding young people are being created that are resistant to heat, water shortage, insects and other factors. In this regard, it is important to expand scientific research works on the creation and introduction into production of new selected varieties of agricultural crops that are resistant to diseases and pests, suitable for soil and climate conditions. In order to solve these problems on a global scale, the widespread use of various breeding methods that are widely used in other agricultural crops in cotton selection is relevant. Broad involvement in the selection process to overcome this problem is necessary, that is, the best single selections collected in field conditions Verticillium dahliae Kleb fungus and Xanthomonas malvacearum bacteria,

It will be possible to choose complex resistant forms of cotton.

Cotton is grown abroad and in our Republic for fiber. This is why the fiber is released the sign is considered as one of the most important indicators.

Newly created 39.2 in the T-116 ridge when we study the ridges according to the fiber yield indicator ranged from percent to 40.0 percent, i.e. 39.2 percent in 1st repetition, 2nd repetition it was 40.0 percent and 39.6 percent in the 3rd iteration.

From 38.7 percent in the T-1094 ridge it was in the range of 40.1 percent. In the range of T-403 from 38.5 percent to 41.7 percent was 38.5% in the 1st repetition, 41.7% in the 2nd repetition, and 39.3% in the 3rd repetition percent. According to the indicator of fiber output of new ridges when we studied, we obtained almost similar indicators in all ridges.

Damage to newly created ridges by wilt and gommosis, some morphological characters and fiber quality indicators

varieties	Gommoz with illness damage	Wilt disease with damage	One piece	Fiber out	1000 piece seed	Mic	Mic	Lend (dyu)	UI (%)	Str (g/t ex)
-----------	----------------------------	--------------------------	-----------	-----------	-----------------	-----	-----	------------	--------	--------------

	Spring phase (%)	Autumn phase (%)	All right degree (%)	Strong degree (%)	pocket weight	put (%)	weight					
T-3384												
I-repeat	6.0	2.0	2.0	-	5.6	39.2	117.6	4.5	157	1.15	84.8	31.1
II- repeat	6.0	4.0	4.0	2.0	6.0	40.0	116.4	4.4	153	1.16	85.1	32.2
III- repeat	2.0	4.0	2.0	-	5.9	39.6	120.3	4.5	163	1.21	86.0	33.8
T-3385												
I- repeat	6.0	2.0	2.0	-	5.7	38.7	121.6	4.5	158	1.15	85.8	32.0
II- repeat	2.0	-	4.	2.0	5.7	39.2	118.4	4.4	171	1.21	84.3	36.4
III- repeat	2.0	2.0	-	2.0	5.8	39.8	117.8	4.5	170	1.19	84.7	36.2
T-3386												
I- repeat	6.0	2.0	-	-	5.8	38.5	123.2	4.3	156	1.15	86.8	33.5
II- repeat	2.0	-	2.0	-	5.6	40.1	117.4	4.2	161	1.19	83.9	34.5
III- repeat	4.0	4.0	2.0	-	6.0	39.3	119.6	4.3	159	1.18	84.5	33.5

1000 seed weight at high yield of cotton indicator is of great importance. 1000 seed weight of new ridges 120.3 out of 116.4 grams in the T-116 series ranged from 1 to 20 grams, i.e. 117.6 grams in the 1st repetition, 116.4 in the 2nd repetition gram and in the 3rd repetition it was 120.3 grams. 117.8 on the T-1094 ridge ranged from gram to 121.6 grams. From 117.4 grams in the T-403 range

It was in the range of 123.2 grams, that is, 123.2 grams in the 1st repetition, 123.2 grams in the 2nd repetition It was 117.4 grams and in the 3rd repetition 119.6 grams. 1000 pieces of ridges

compared to the T-403 range, a higher index when studied by seed weight organized (Table -1)

References:

- 1.Barotova A., Raxmatullayev S., Ismoilova A. DEFINING THE SEED FIBER RESIDUE AND WEIGHT OF 1000 SEEDS IN COTTON VARIETIES //Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture. - 2023. - T. 3. - №. 2. - C. 22-25.

2.

Barotova A. et al. EVALUATION OF FIBER QUALITY INDEXES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF COTTON PLANTS //Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 41-46.

3. Quvondiqovich, M. B., Ruzievna, K. G., Abduganievich, E. J., Turdikulovich, J. S., Razzakovna, B. A., & Erkinovna, S. G. (2020). Performance Of Fiber Output And Fiber Length In Inter Variety Hybrid Families Of Middle Fiber Cotton. European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine, 7(03), 2020.

4. Jo'rayev, S. T., Ashurov, M., Narmatova, G., Toreev, F., Akhmedov, D., Mavlonova, N., ... & Baratova, A. (2022). Cotton breeding and seed production. LESSON PRESS, 1(1), 224.

5. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Raxmatullayev, S., & Ismoilova, A. (2023). EVALUATION OF FIBER QUALITY INDEXES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF COTTON PLANTS. Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture, 3(2), 41-46.

6. Ergashev, J., Kholmurodova, G., Egamberdiev, R., & Barotova, A. (2023, February). Fiber Consumption and Quality Indicators of Varieties of *G. Hirsutum* L. Type and Interspecific Hybrid Combinations. In XV International Scientific Conference "INTERAGROMASH 2022" Glo. bal Precision Ag Innovation 2022, Volume 2 (pp. 2187-2192). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

7. Баротова, А. Р., Якубжонова, Н. А., & Хуррамов, А. А. (2022). ҒЎЗА НАВЛАРИ СЕЛЕКЦИЯСИДА ҚИММАТЛИ ХЎЖАЛИК БЕЛГИЛАРНИНГ ИРСИЙЛАНИШИ, ЎЗГАРУВЧАНЛИГИ ВА ШАКЛЛАНИШИ. European Journal of Interdisciplinary Research and Development, 10, 318-321.

8. Холмуродова, Г. Р., Джумаева, Г. П., & Зайнобиддинова, З. (2018). ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ НЕКОТОРЫХ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ПРИЗНАКОВ СЕМЕЙ И ЛИНИЙ ХЛОПЧАТНИКА, СОЗДАНЫХ МЕТОДОМ СЛОЖНОЙ ГИБРИДИЗАЦИИ. Актуальные проблемы современной науки, (4), 200-204.

9. Razzakovna, B. A. (2022). G 'O 'ZA OILALARIDA SELEKSIYASIDA QIMMATLI XO 'JALIK BELGI KO'RSATKICHLARINING O'ZGARUVCHANLIGI VA SHAKLLANISHI. JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 2(13), 479-481.

10. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Mamadaliyev, A. B., & Jo'rayev, O. (2023). INHERITANCE, VARIABILITY AND FORMATION OF FERTILITY ELEMENTS IN COTTON. Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture, 3(3), 20-23.

11. Kholmurodova, G., Barotova, A., Namazov, S., Yuldasheva, R., & Jumashev, M. (2023, January). Creation of selected items with high fiber yield and length based on cotton composite hybrids. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 371, p. 01039).

12. Yakubjonova, N., & Sherboyev, S. (2023). SABZAVOT LOVIYASI KOLLEKSIYA NAV NAMUNALARI OQSIL MIQDORINING TAHLILI. Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук, 3(4), 111-115.

13. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Mamadaliyev, A. B., & Jo'rayev, O. (2023). FIBER LENGTH AND QUALITY INDICATORS IN COTTON VARIETIES. Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture, 3(3), 50-53.

14. Kholmurodova, G. R., Mirkhomidova, N. A., Yuldasheva, R. A., Nazarova, M. B., Barotova, A. R., & Aktamova, I. A. (2023, March). Creation of goods with high fiber quality from the selection of varieties belonging to *G. Hirsutum* L. species. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1142, No. 1, p. 012089). IOP Publishing.

15.

Kholmurodova, G. R., Yuldasheva, R. A., Barotova, A. R., Yakubjanova, N. A., Khakimova, M. M., & Aktamova, I. A. (2023, March). Correlation between family and range value economic traits in cotton. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1142, No. 1, p. 012075). IOP Publishing.

16. Barotova, A., Xurramov, A., Raxmatullayev, S., & Ismoilova, A. (2023). EVALUATION OF FIBER QUALITY INDEXES IN DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF COTTON PLANTS. *Journal of Agriculture & Horticulture*, 3(2), 41-46.

17. Kholmurodova, G., Barotova, A., Namazov, S., Yuldasheva, R., & Jumashv, M. (2023, January). Creation of selected items with high fiber yield and length based on cotton composite hybrids. In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 371, p. 01039).

18. Juraev, S. T., & Yakubjonova, N. A. (2022). ANALYSIS OF VALUE-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INTROGRESSIVE HYBRIDS OF COTTON UNDER DIFFERENT SOIL-CLIMATE CONDITIONS IN UZBEKISTAN. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 1638-1646.

19. Abdullayeva, B., & Yakubjonova, N. (2023). TYPOLOGICAL FEATURES OF COMBINING BIOLOGY AND GENETICS BASED ON AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(3), 39-41.

20. Yakubjonova, N. (2023). GENERAL FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF BIOLOGY AND GENETICS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(3), 52-54.

21. Azizov, M. B., Aberkulov, M. N., Yakubjonova, N. A., & Khayrullayev, S. S. (2021). Efficiency of mixed sowing of maize with forage beet in irrigated meadow sierozem soils of Uzbekistan. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(8), 316-320.

22. Azizov, B. M., Jumashv, M. M., Yakubjonova, N. A., & KHAYRULLAYEV, S. (2021). EFFECT OF SOWING RATE ON THE QUALITY OF SEEDS OF WINTER WHEAT. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 755-760.

